

Report on the Multiplier Event: Speaking BESPOC with Practitioners (LibOCS Multiplier Event)

Link to this file: [LibOCS ME5 Evaluation Report](#)

Introduction

On April 17, 2024, the LibOCS project organized an online Multiplier Event titled "Speaking BESPOC with Practitioners." The event aimed to promote the BESPOC (Broad Engagement in Science, Point of Contact) model and discuss institutional support for Citizen Science (CS). This report combines the results of the assessment forms collected from external participants and the internal evaluation conducted by the LibOCS team.

Event Details

Date: April 17, 2024

Event Title: Speaking BESPOC with Practitioners (LibOCS Multiplier Event)

Format: Online

This [LibOCS folder \(shared on our GDrive\)](#) contains:

- all presentation slides
- the registration
- screenshots with actual participation
- the raw evaluation data

Agenda and Speakers

- **14:00-14:10 LibOCS Project: A Short Introduction**, Speaker: Lilian Neerut (Tartu University)
- **14:10-14:30 The BESPOC Model At a Glance**, Speakers: Tiberius Ignat (Immer Besser, LibOCS Partner)
- **14:30-15:00 BESPOC Implementation at Baltic Universities**, Speakers: Gita Rosenberga (University of Latvia), Tuuliki Tõiste (TalTech University, Tallinn), Aiste Pranckutė (Kaunas University of Technology), Lilian Neerut (Tartu University)
- **15:00-15:15 A Compass for a Citizen Science Hub: How the BESPOC Model Helped Shape Our Contact Point**, Speaker: Dr. Floor Keersmaekers (Vrije Universiteit Brussel)
- **15:15-15:45 Questions, Answers, Dialogue with Participants**

Participation Data

- **Registrants:** 175
- **Actual Participants:** 75

External Evaluation

Participant Feedback

Relevance of the Event

Participants rated the relevance of the event on a scale from 1 to 10:

- 7: 1
- 8: 3
- 9: 2
- 10: 10

Importance of Institutional Support for CS

Participants rated the importance of having access to an institutional support service for CS:

- 7: 1
- 8: 1
- 9: 1
- 10: 10

Main Takeaways

Participants shared their main takeaways from the event:

1. I will ensure that data collected through citizen science projects is properly curated, preserved, and accessible for future use.
2. I will provide books, online courses, and other educational materials to help citizens understand scientific principles and methodologies.
3. Knowledge support.
4. Citizen Science needs support services from my university.
5. LOGISTIC.
6. Financial support is needed for sustainability.
7. Citizen science is necessary; we need answers to generalized problems. No more science from the office; it needs to touch reality.
8. The experience from other libraries, how to start implementing CS activities in HEI.
9. Every institution has different situations and contexts.
10. Sharing different points of view in science is an enriching way to enhance researchers' expertise.

Suggested Topics for Future Webinars

Participants suggested the following topics for future webinars:

1. Cultural Sensitivity
2. Funding and Grants

3. Engaging the Local Community
4. Access to Data and Technology
5. Environmental monitoring, invasive species, biodiversity
6. Public engagement for research
7. Citizen Science Templates
8. BESPOC
9. Personal Organization
10. Case studies: good practices and lessons learnt from failures
11. The water problem at the global level
12. Engaging citizens, science communication
13. Specific examples and experience
14. Epistemic models in science, how every epistemic model makes science.

Demographic Data

Gender: 46.2% female, 53.8% male

Profession:

- Researcher: 7.7%
- Research Manager or Administrator: 23.1%
- Professor / Teacher / Lecturer: 23.1%
- Research Librarian: 23.1%
- Consultant: 15.4%
- PhD Student: 7.7%
- Other: 14.3%

Internal Evaluation

Participant Feedback

Relevance of the Event

LibOCS participants rated the relevance of the event on a scale from 1 to 10:

- 10: 4

Importance of Institutional Support for CS

LibOCS participants rated the importance of having access to an institutional support service for CS:

- 8: 1
- 10: 3

Main Takeaways

LibOCS participants shared their main takeaways:

1. Universities should think more institutionally about CS.
2. Such services develop slowly. Libraries have to work very hard to prove themselves as a player.
3. It is necessary to involve researchers in the planning process to know what they really need and want.
4. What kind of support they need the most at the institutional level.

Suggested Topics for Future Webinars

LibOCS participants suggested the following topics for future webinars:

1. BESPOC Framework
2. Citizen Science techniques
3. Practical examples
4. Experience stories
5. Case studies of lessons learned from institutions that have implemented BESPOC at least to some level.

Demographic Data

Profession:

- Researcher: 25%
- Research Librarian: 50%
- Other: 25%

Conclusion

The Multiplier Event "Speaking BESPOC with Practitioners" successfully engaged a diverse group of participants and highlighted the critical role of institutional support for Citizen Science. Both external and internal evaluations indicate a strong interest in further exploring the BESPOC model and the role of libraries in supporting CS. The feedback gathered will guide further dissemination strategies for the LibOCS project, the organisation of future webinars, and the enhancement of the LibOCS project's efforts to promote and implement effective support structures for Citizen Science.